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LETTER TO EDITOR
COVID-19 PANDEMIC AND CONVENTIONAL TRANSBRONCHIAL NEEDLE
ASPIRATION IN THE DEVELOPING WORLD

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Dear Editor:

Over the period of past 10 years endobronchial ultrasound guided transbronchial needle aspiration (EBUS-TBNA) has gained much popularity among Indian Interventional Pulmonologists. Unintentionally, the conventional TBNA is underutilized and the skill is fast fading. (1, 2)

Incidentally, in the developing world the practice and upkeep of EBUS-TBNA is extremely expensive. Besides, getting a prompt repair of a damaged EBUS scope is also challenging. Needless to say, that this delay is further compounded by the COVID-19 pandemic and the lockdown of the country. It is also realized that the luxury of a spare or a loaner scope is almost non-existent in India.

	Age/ Gender	Indication	Differential diagnosis	Size (mm)	Station	Microbiology	Cytology	Final diagnosis
1	39/F	Asymptomatic	Tuberculosis	24	7	Gene Xpert+	Lymphocytes	Tuberculosis
2	28/F	Fever	Tuberculosis	18	7	Gene Xpert +	Granuloma	Tuberculosis
3	57/F	Fever	CA lung/ Lymphoma	24	11R	Gene Xpert -	Malignant cells	Plasma cell Dyscrasia
4	42/M	Fever	Tuberculosis/ Lymphoma	7: 20 4R: 22	7, 4R	Gene Xpert +	Granuloma	Tuberculosis
5	70/F	Fever	Tuberculosis/ Lymphoma	28	7	Gene Xpert -	Reactive	Reactive
6	56/M	Chronic cough	Tuberculosis/ Sarcoidosis	7:24, 4R:20	7, 4R	Gene Xpert -	Granuloma	Sarcoidosis
7	18/M	Fever	Tuberculosis/ Sarcoidosis	7:22 4R:24	7, 4R	Gene Xpert-	Granuloma	Tuberculosis
8	28/M	Fever	Tuberculosis/ Sarcoidosis	21	7	Gene Xpert -	Granuloma	Tuberculosis

9	39/M	Fever	Tuberculosis/ Sarcoidosis	7:22 4R:1 8 11R: 20	7,4R, 11R	Gene Xpert -	Granuloma in all	Sarcoidosis
10	62/F	PET avid node	CA Gall bladder	7:22 4R:2 0	4 R, 7	Gene Xpert -	Reactive	Reactive
11	70/M	PET avid node	CA lung	18	7	Gene Xpert -	Malignant cells	Adenocarcinoma

In our case an EBUS scope went out for a repair on 12th March, 2020 with an arrangement for a quick replacement. Unfortunately, due to the total national lockdown it never happened. The scenario was similar to that before acquiring the EBUS scope. During the following eight weeks, we encountered 13 cases with mediastinal masses and enlarged lymph nodes (LN) who would have customarily undergone diagnostic or staging EBUS-TBNA. As delay in establishing the diagnosis was not an option, we chose to perform conventional – TBNA (C-TBNA) in selected cases (11) with LN at stations 4 R, 7 and 11 with short axis diameter of 15 mm or greater. The procedure was performed by a single bronchoscopist (PG) with a 21-G Olympus needle (NA 601D-1519). [PG was trained with C-TBNA during her post graduate training and senior residency (2001-2007) and had performed 30-50 cases per year. She had stopped performing the procedure since acquiring EBUS scope in year 2016] Four to five passes were made at each station. No rapid onsite examination (ROSE) was available. The material aspirated – partly was spread into a thin smear on slides and rest was flushed with saline and collected in cytolyte ® solution. A part of the flushed material was sent for microbiological analysis gene Xpert for M tuberculosis, AFB culture and cytological examination.

A definite diagnosis could be established in all (100%); 5 (46%) Mycobacterium Tuberculosis, 2 (18%) Sarcoidosis, 2 (18%) Malignancies (Plasma cell tumor and Adenocarcinoma) and 2 (18%) reactive lymph nodes. In the latter 2 cases results was compatible with the clinical suspicion of benign condition. Material was adequate in all samples as commented by the pathologist. [Table: 1]

Conventional TBNA is still a useful diagnostic tool, especially in the developing world with the prevalence of M.TB. It can aid in timely diagnosis of various benign and malignant mediastinal pathologies, especially when the LNs are larger than 15 mm size and located at favorable stations. All contemporary pulmonologists should essentially gather the skills. It has been previously shown that the yield of C-TBNA and EBUS-TBNA is equal for the station 7 and 4R when the size of LN is greater than 15 mm.^(3,4) In that respect C-TBNA can increase the cost effectiveness of diagnostic bronchoscopy in the developing world.⁽⁵⁾ Table 1: Patient profile, procedure details and final diagnosis

F = Female, M =Male, Ca= Carcinoma, PET =Positron Emission Tomography

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